

Usage of the BINGO alarm by EMB-314 Super Tucano operators

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Abstract – The minimum recovery fuel for the Super Tucano aircraft, called BINGO, is calculated before the mission, and recalculated in flight based on distance and fuel flow information. The Super Tucano has visual and audible alarms that can be configured to indicate this minimum fuel. Using these alarms will ensure that the aircraft will land within the set minimums, while not using them may result in a landing with the fuel below the set minimums.

Keywords – Flight planning, Flight Safety, Fuel Management.

I. INTRODUCTION

Super Tucano pilots need to constantly monitor the aircraft's fuel during flight to determine if they can land with a minimum of pre-established fuel. Currently, in the Brazilian Air Force's Joker Squadron, this minimum pickup fuel, called BINGO, is calculated before the mission, and recalculated in flight based on distance and fuel flow information. The Super Tucano has EICAS functions that are underutilized and can reduce the workload of pilots, as well as contribute to flight safety.

II. THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

A. The concept of BINGO

The Brazilian fighter aviation defines BINGO as the predetermined amount of minimum fuel to return to base [1]. NATO members use as a BINGO concept the amount of fuel needed to return to base. [2]

The A-29 Aircraft Procedure Manual defines that BINGO should be the remaining fuel value which allows the return for full-stop landing with 120kg (A-29B) or 180kg (A-29A). To establish this value, it's added 40kg of fuel consumed on the recovery in local flights and 20kg more for visual approaches or 40kg for instrument approaches [1].

Once the fuel is less than the minimum provided for a given stage of the flight, it's required that the aircraft return to base (escorted when in formation) or even the entire flight. The BINGO fuel represents a more restricted situation and should be considered as the minimum fuel for recovery. Therefore, a very high BINGO should not be planned, because, by doctrine, when reaching it, that aircraft must return to base [1].

B. The Super Tucano

The Super Tucano has visual and audible alarms and the Pilot Fault List (PFL) page to inform the pilot, in addition to the system status and failures, the existence of abnormal configuration [3].

The Mission Computer (MDP), through the Engine Information and Crew Alert System (EICAS), controls the setups made by the pilot for the mission, activating visual alerts when the activation conditions are met [3].

Alert messages are provided at three different levels, including "CAUTION" messages in yellow, in addition to voice messages whenever a condition is identified for which the pilot is to be alerted, which are issued twice for system failures and for cases requiring immediate action by the pilot [3].

When the amount of fuel remaining on the aircraft is equal to or less than the sum of the BINGO value entered in the UFCP FUEL format added to the amount of fuel to be consumed in optimal profile for the Home Point (HP) defined in the planning, EICAS displays the message of type "CAUTION" BINGO, in addition to a BINGO sound alert repeated twice [3].

The UFCP CRUS format allows the aircraft to be guided through an optimal vertical profile to the control point selected as Home Point (HP). The profile is calculated to maintain minimal consumption on cruise based on the current position and configuration of the aircraft, HP position, wind, and temperature [3]. It's provided in this format, in addition to other parameters, the remaining fuel at 3000ft overhead the HP.

You must fill in the "BINGO Quantity" field in UFCP FUEL format with the amount of fuel you want to reach overhead the control point identified as Home Point. The BINGO quantity can be entered through the DTC.

The configuration example in the Flight Manual - Supplementary Manual of the Avionics System of the UFCP FUEL format shows the insertion of 300kg in the field "BINGO Quantity".

The Super Tucano also allows, through the TRIP page 0 of the STANDALONEGPS, to configure the information of true speed (ktas) and wind direction and intensity, and via page TRIP 1, select the destination airfield, adjust the fuel flow (according to EICAS), and select the desired fuel at the destination (usually 160kg). With this, you will have the indication, continuously calculated, of the fuel needed to reach your destination if you fly directly to it [1].

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Setup

It is understood that, although the definitions of different sources are similar but not equal, knowledge and doctrine are disseminated globally, and all agents seek the same goal.

According to the A-29 Aircraft Procedure Manual, there are basically four fuel configuration scenarios that the aircraft needs to be overhead the airfield, considering 20kg for a VFR

procedure, 40kg for an IFR procedure, 120kg for landing the A-29B and 180kg for landing the A-29A:

TABLE I. EARLY PROCEDURE MINIMUMS FOR LANDING.

<i>Recovery conditions</i>	<i>A-29A</i>	<i>A-29B</i>
VFR	200kg	140kg
IFR	220kg	160kg

In Super Tucano, in addition to calculating in hand in flight, there are two tools to help reach the destination with the above configuration: The BINGO function of EICAS, and the Trip page of the STANDALONE GPS.

On the Trip page, the A-29 Aircraft Procedure Manual suggests inserting 160kg as desired fuel at the destination for Radio Navigation missions, compatible with the table above, and considering the normal operation of the A-29B in the Joker Squadron, responsible for writing this chapter.

Better than using this page is the BINGO function of EICAS, which, in addition to reducing the pilot's workload of entering the data of speed, wind and fuel flow, it already extracts this information from the various sensors of the plane and the configuration entered by the pilot.

Entering one of the values in the above table in UFCP FUEL format will ensure that, once the BINGO alarm is activated, if the pilot follows the profile established by the CRUS format, he will reach overhead the airfield at 3000ft, ensuring a full-stop landing with 120kg on the A-29B or 180kg on the A-29A.

If the pilot keeps the BINGO Quantity at 120kg, when activating the alarm, the aircraft will reach overhead the airfield at 3000ft with 120kg which, at best, will allow a landing (after a Peel-off Traffic) with 115kg, below the established minimums or, at worst (after an IFR procedure), will land with 80kg, already at risk of engine flameout and in an emergency.

It is important to note that the activation of the BINGO alarm does not characterize an emergency itself, but only an alert to the pilot, which is a function of EICAS. The pilot, upon receiving the alarm, should redouble his attention to fuel control and know that when flying below the calculated minimum, he/she may land below the predicted minimum.

IV. CONCLUSION

Entering the values of the above table in the UFCP FUEL format will ensure that the aircraft will land within the established minimums, since the pilot, in addition to using the BINGO that he calculated manually, will have visual and audible alarms. On the other hand, using the value 120kg will not be an indication, since the pilot will have to have decided to return to base before this alarm. If the pilot has not yet started the recall, the activation of the alarm will simply be a reminder that the pilot is no longer able to meet the minimums, which is not the purpose of EICAS.

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